

Event metadata

Event title	Leveraging deep learning to design custom protein-binding proteins
Event type	Webinar series
Date of event	15 July - 11 November 2025
Topic description	<p>Deep learning methods are speeding up the process of designing proteins with desirable biophysical properties. This fast moving field leverages computational workflows that integrate deep learning models like RFdiffusion, ProteinMPNN, Bindcraft with protein structural prediction methods (Alphafold, Chai-1, Boltz-2) and traditional structural biology methods to improve protein design success rates.</p> <p>This webinar series features case studies from leaders in the field and is designed to inspire and help you recognise potential applications of this new approach to the design of protein-binding-proteins. Join us to hear how software such as Bindcraft is being applied to different research questions and gain hints and tips on using them in your own work.</p> <p>This series is brought to you by the Community for Structural Biology Computing in Australia.</p>
Speakers	<p>Dr Rhys Grinter, University of Melbourne Dr Cyntia Taveneau, Monash University Dr Richard Birkinshaw, WEHI Dr Josh Hardy, WEHI Professor Joel Mackay, University of Sydney</p>
Format description	A series of webinar presentations followed by a brief question and answer session
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/protein-binder-series
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Keywords	Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091 Structural biology http://edamontology.org/topic_1317 Protein interactions http://edamontology.org/topic_0128 AI Deep learning
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	These webinars are intended for structural biologists but are suitable for anyone who is curious about <i>de novo</i> protein design.
Prerequisites	None
Technical requirements	None
Learning outcomes	By the end of this webinar series you should be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe multiple use case of deep learning in the design of custom protein-binding-proteins
Training materials	<p><i>Using AI protein design to design binding proteins to challenging bacterial transporters</i> - Dr Rhys Grinter, University of Melbourne</p> <p>Recording: https://youtu.be/3Ad2gUjeSL8</p> <p>Slides: https://zenodo.org/records/16511653</p> <p><i>Alcrs: AI-Designed Anti-CRISPRs as Programmable CRISPR Inhibitors</i>- Dr Cyntia Taveneau, Monash University</p> <p>Recording: https://youtu.be/GSoOfyJUySA</p> <p>Slides: https://zenodo.org/records/17033917</p> <p><i>Using in silico design methods to create de novo proteins that selectively modulate apoptosis</i>- Dr Richard Birkinshaw, WEHI</p> <p>Recording: https://youtu.be/9-3sHy1ybpE</p> <p>Slides: https://zenodo.org/records/17148914</p>

Introducing ProteinDJ: A modular and open-source framework for protein design workflows - Dr Josh Hardy, WEHI

Recording: <https://youtu.be/xwvF62HxaF0>

Slides: <https://zenodo.org/uploads/17337232>

Baby steps in the AI-guided design of proteins to modulate gene transcription - Professor Joel Mackay, University of Sydney

Recording: <https://youtu.be/tKqH8WikIX4>

Slides: <https://zenodo.org/records/17605782>